

DEVELOPMENT OF DENTAL PREVENTIVE MEASURES FOR PSYCHIATRIC DISPENSARY PATIENTS

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Abstract. *Currently, the majority of patients seeking dental care suffer from various forms of periodontal disease. Modern epidemiological data show not only the significant prevalence of periodontal pathology in children and adults, but also the impact of dental plaque, oral hygiene, poor-quality prostheses and fillings, dentoalveolar deformations, occlusal damage, acceleration of occlusal damage. the tissues of the vestibule of the oral cavity and respiratory properties of the oral cavity; used drugs, previous and accompanying diseases, extreme factors that lead to violation of compensatory mechanisms of natural immunity, etc.*

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The increase in the pathology of the organs and tissues of the oral cavity cannot be stopped by therapeutic measures. In this regard, it is necessary to develop and widely implement measures aimed at preventing the main dental diseases.

To date, the relationship between the condition of the periodontium and the level of individual oral hygiene has been proven. Soft dental plaque accumulated in the area of the necks of the teeth and in the interdental spaces helps to start the mechanism of destruction of the entire periodontal complex, starting with inflammation of the gums and disruption of the periodontal joint. ends with a severe destructive process in the bone tissue of the alveolar processes of the jaws.

Despite the availability of various hygiene products on the modern market, the state of oral hygiene in a large part of the population remains unsatisfactory. Based on the above, it should be considered that the need to prevent dental diseases is generally recognized, therefore, all patients who initially come to the dental clinic should be encouraged to perform oral hygiene using preventive measures. They must be sure to demonstrate the quality of their care using coloring solutions, tell about the leading role of microbial factors in the emergence and development of inflammatory periodontal diseases.

About 15-20 teeth that a person loses between the ages of 40-65 are most often caused by periodontitis, and in cases of partial or complete toothlessness, a large amount of money is spent on restoring the chewing function. Orthopedic treatment of patients with periodontal disease is the most expensive dental service worldwide. Maintaining dental health determines not only the normal functioning of the dental system and the entire human body, but also the quality of life.

The main etiological factor should be recognized as the microflora of the oral cavity. In other words, non-observance or poor oral hygiene as the main risk factor undoubtedly leads to gingivitis and caries. According to WHO (2002), about 95% of the adult population of the planet and 80% of children have certain symptoms of periodontopathy.

To prevent periodontal diseases in the early stages, professional hygiene of the oral cavity, including training in the rules of oral hygiene, monitoring their implementation and constantly encouraging the patient during the first and subsequent courses of treatment is the most effective. Therefore, it is necessary to pay special attention to the introduction, teaching and monitoring of oral hygiene in early childhood and in the growing period of the child. Only the optimization and strengthening of oral hygiene solves caries disease and gingivitis as the starting point of periodontitis, because dental plaque and dental plaque have a negative effect on both the hard tissues of the tooth and the periodontium.

Prevention is a system of state, social, hygienic and medical measures aimed at ensuring a high level of health, preventing diseases of the oral cavity and the whole body. The main goal of prevention is to eliminate the causes and conditions of the occurrence and development of diseases, as well as to increase the body's resistance to the effects of adverse environmental factors.

According to the WHO classification, prevention is usually divided into primary, secondary and tertiary. Primary prevention is the use of methods and tools to prevent the occurrence of dental diseases. If the first signs of damage appear, as a result of preventive measures, they can be stabilized or reverse their development.

Primary prevention methods include:

- individual oral hygiene;
- professional oral hygiene;
- endogenous use of fluoride preparations;
- use of local preventive means;
- dental education of the population.

Personal hygiene involves the removal of dental plaque from the tooth and gum surfaces by the patient himself using various hygiene tools (toothbrushes, toothpastes and gels, gums, elixirs, rinses, interdental oral cavity hygiene tools). involves careful and regular removal. The best way to prevent the development of periodontal disease is to completely remove plaque from the teeth through professional oral hygiene. The presence of a pathological process in periodontal tissues is determined by the condition of the gums. The criteria of healthy gums are pink color, tips of interdental papillae, tissue density and absence of bleeding. Inflammatory events in the gums are characterized by the following signs: hyperemia, cyanosis, swelling. The goal of professional oral hygiene is to prevent and treat diseases of the hard tissues of the teeth and oral mucosa. The term "professional oral hygiene" refers to the thorough removal of soft and hard dental plaque from all surfaces of the teeth and subsequent treatment of the teeth and gums with preventive means.

Professional oral hygiene includes several consecutive activities:

Having a conversation with the patient about the need to observe professional hygiene of the oral cavity, the danger of dental plaque and dental deposits on the hard tissues of the teeth and gums, and forming a correct understanding of the importance of this issue in the patient. Teaching the patient, the rules of personal oral hygiene. Conducted over several visits. Preparation of the oral cavity consists of irrigation with a weak antiseptic solution.

Dental plaque removal. Dental plaque removal includes removing plaque, tartar, grinding and polishing the teeth. It is recommended to remove tartar not immediately, but in several visits, especially if they occupy large areas on different surfaces of the teeth. Covering the tooth surface with fluoride-containing or remineralizing preparations. Secondary prevention is the use of

conventional treatment methods to stop the developing pathological process and tissue preservation. These methods include the treatment of dental caries (fillings, endodontic procedures), therapeutic and surgical treatment of periodontal diseases, and treatment of other diseases of the oral cavity.

Tertiary prevention is the restoration of lost function with the help of means that replace lost tissues and the rehabilitation of patients, bringing their condition to a normal state as much as possible. It is necessary to optimize and strengthen hygienic education of the population. Today, oral hygiene should be taught not only to children, but also to their parents. Only comprehensive dental educational work activates auditory and visual motivation, improves hygienic skills and theoretical knowledge of dental health. Optimization and intensification of oral hygiene consists of targeted use of motivational methods of hygienic education, professional oral hygiene, use of clinically and economically effective modern drugs. It is necessary to create a theoretical basis, to strive for the development of knowledge activity among the population, to arouse interest and passion for information, as well as to form manual skills, to maintain and improve hygienic knowledge and skills.

REFERENCES

1. Zoyirov T. E. et al. PROCESSES AND THEIR COMPLICATIONS IN THE FACE-JAW AREA AND ORAL MUCOSA OF PATIENTS SUFFERING FROM KOVID-19 INFECTION //SUSTAINABILITY OF EDUCATION, SOCIO-ECONOMIC SCIENCE THEORY. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 6. – С. 17-19.
2. Каххоровна R. B. et al. IMPROVEMENT OF THERAPEUTIC MEASURES FOR CHANGES IN THE MUCOUS MEMBRANE OF THE ORAL CAVITY AND TONGUE OF THE PATIENT IN THE POSTOPERATIVE BARIATRIC STATE //International Journal of Medical Sciences And Clinical Research. – 2024. – Т. 4. – №. 01. – С. 31-36.
3. Рахмонова B., Мухаммадқулов V. IMPROVING THERAPEUTIC MEASURES FOR CHANGES IN THE ORAL MUCOSA AND TONGUE OF THE PATIENT IN A POSTOPERATIVE BARIATRIC CONDITION //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 576-579.
4. Каххаровна R. B. et al. YUZ VA JAGDA ZAMONAVIY ENDOSKOPIK JARROHLIKNING YUTUQ VA KAMCHILIKLARI //Journal of Integrated Education and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 72-76.
5. Ибрагимов Д. Д., Гаффаров У. Б., Рахмонова Б. К. КОВИД-19 ИНФЕКЦИЯСИ БИЛАН ОГРИГАН БЕМОРЛАРНИНГ ЮЗ-ЖАГ СОХАСИДА ВА ОГИЗ БУШЛИГИ ШИЛЛИК КАВАТЛАРИДА КЕЧАДИГАН ЖАРАЁНЛАР ВА УЛАРНИНГ //Инновационные исследования в современном мире: теория и практика. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 25. – С. 107-109.
6. Sarkisova, V., Lapasova, Z., & Shernazarov, F. (2023). O. Rakhmanov INFLAMMATORY DISEASES OF THE PELVIC WOMEN ORGANS.
7. Shernazarov I., Shernazarov F. Problems of translation of features related to the way of life of peoples //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. B1. – С. 80-83.
8. Jalalova, D., Axmedov, A., Kuryazov, A., & Shernazarov, F. (2022). COMBINED DENTAL AND EYE PATHOLOGY. Science and innovation, 1(8), 91-100.

9. Shernazarov F., Zuhridinovna J. D. Microcirculation disorders in the vascular system of the bulbar conjunctiva in the initial manifestations of cerebral blood supply deficiency //Science and innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. Special Issue 2. – С. 515-522.
10. Solovyova, Y., Prostyakova, N., Sharapova, D., & Shernazarov, F. (2023). The relevance of psychotic disorders in the acute period of a stroke. Science and innovation, 2(D12), 212-217.
11. Rotanov, A., Karshiyev, Z., Sharapova, D., & Shernazarov, F. (2023). Diagnosis of depressive and suicidal spectrum disorders in students of a secondary special education institution. Science and innovation, 2(D11), 309-315.
12. Shernazarov F. COMBINED DENTAL AND EYE PATHOLOGY //Science and Innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 8. – С. 91-100.
13. Raxmonova B., Xaydarova D., Sadikova S. TREATMENT OF FRACTURES OF THE UPPER AND LOWER HEAD IN ELDERLY PATIENTS USING THE IMMOBILIZATION METHOD IMPACT ON PERIODONTAL TISSUE //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D10. – С. 194-198.
14. Kakhorovna R. B. et al. IMPROVING THE SURGICAL METHOD OF SCAR MICROSTOMY //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2023. – Т. 11. – №. 9. – С. 300-304.
15. Farrukh S. ORGANIZATION OF DIGITALIZED MEDICINE AND HEALTH ACADEMY AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN MEDICINE //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. Special Issue 8. – С. 493-499.
16. Kakharovna R. B., Mekhrojiddinovich B. X. MODERN ENDOSCOPIC SURGERY ON THE FACE AND JAW ACHIEVEMENTS AND DISADVANTAGES //O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 17. – С. 136-141.
17. Kakhkhorovna R. B. CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE DISSEMINATED PERIODONTITIS IN INFECTED PATIENTS Entry. Finland International Scientific Journal of Education //Social Science & Humanities. – 2023. – Т. 11. – №. 4. – С. 2095-2103.
18. Рахманова Б. К. и др. ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ И НЕДОСТАТКИ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ЭНДОСКОПИЧЕСКОЙ ХИРУРГИИ ЛИЦА И ЧЕЛЮСТИ //O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 17. – С. 129-135.